

FIELD AND MODEL INVESTIGATION OF THE CLAY LAYER'S PERMEABILITY IN THE FAULT ZONE NEAR THE PAKS II NPP

Maria V. Vilkina^{1,2}, Anton M. Nikulenkov^{1,2}, Vyacheslav G. Rumynin^{1,2}

¹St. Petersburg subdivision of the Institute of the Environmental Geology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Sredny Ave 41, 199004 Saint-Petersburg. E-mail: wilkina.mari@hgepro.ru, annik@hgepro.ru, remynin@hgepro.ru
²St. Petersburg State University, Universitetskaya emb., 7–9, 199034 Saint-Petersburg.

ABSTRACT: *The construction of the nuclear power plant is an advanced engineering task that can be sufficiently impeded by the complicated hydrogeological conditions. A 23-meter-deep pit for Paks II NPP is preceded by the execution of the cut-off wall along the pit's perimeter. Yet, for maximum efficiency of the cut-off wall construction, it is recommended to deepen its basement to the level of the continuous aquitard. As the construction site of Paks II NPP is located within the regional fault zone with a 100-meter vertical amplitude, the deformation of the clay layer could be accompanied by the layer's continuity break. To validate this assumption, a comprehensive geological and hydrogeological study at the construction site was performed. It included the methods of geophysics, borehole drilling, core description, pumping tests, and numerical modeling. The investigation has revealed the insufficiency of solely geological methods' results for conceptualizing hydrogeological conditions. Nothing but a combination of several geological and hydrogeological methods allowed for the identification of the plicative clay layer's deformation.*

Key words: *fault zone hydrogeology, plicative deformation, nuclear power plant, hydraulic tomography, numerical hydrogeological modeling*

INTRODUCTION

At the beginning of 2024, there were 100 power units operating in the European Union. They produce up to a quarter of all the electricity consumed in the region. Four of these units belong to the Hungarian nuclear power plant (NPP) in Paks. The Paks II NPP project implements the construction of two more: 5th and 6th nuclear units (NI), 100 m to the north from the operating Paks NPP. To limit the groundwater inflow into the 23-meter-deep construction pit and minimize the hydraulic impact on the operating Paks NPP, the cut-off wall (COW) construction along the pit's perimeter is planned to be constructed. To obtain maximum efficiency, the COW's basement is deepened to the elevations of the continuous aquitard. As the presence of the hydrogeological windows in the aquitard might be considered an unfavourable factor for the water protective measures, the degree of the hydrogeological study might be seen as a factor controlling the safety of the Paks II NPP construction and Paks NPP operation.

The hydrogeological settings of the territory under study were determined by the geological structure. Geophysical survey results' have revealed that the regional Dunaszentgyörgy-Harta fault zone crosses the territory of the planned 5th NI from the north-east to the south-west. The vertical displacement along the fault zone has led to the formation of the "graben-like" structure in the sediments. This has defined the hydrogeological schematization of the territory, which can be presented as follows: subhorizontal 30-meters-thick Quarternary aquifer composed of the alluvial sand and gravel (1); Upper Neogene layers of clays and loams, filling up the graben structure that composes a semi-confined aquifer (2); Neogene clay layer that traces the "graben-like" structure (3); Lower Neogene (Pannonian) aquifer composed of the sand (4).

From the hydrogeological description provided above, it is clear that the Neogene clay layer is the one that is considered to be a basement for the COW. Due to the vertical displacement along the fault zone, however, the continuity and impermeability of the clay layer are doubtful. A comprehensive review of the influence of fault zones on hydrogeology is provided in the work of Bense (Bense *et al.* 2013). Conceptually, the deformation of the clay layer at the Paks II NPP construction site could be conceptualized with three scenarios: vertical displacement without a break of the layer's continuity i.e., plicative structure (i) (Fig. 1a); vertical displacement with a series of the small amplitude faults (ii) (Fig. 1b); vertical displacement with a break of the layer's continuity (iii) (Fig. 1c).

Fig. 1. Concepts of the clay layer deformation in the fault zone: i) no discontinuity; ii) local discontinuity; iii) regional discontinuity

The work carried out in the scope of the present study was aimed at identifying which of the suggested scenarios corresponds to the real clay layer's deformation. An overview of the methods used in this study is given below.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The aim of the research was to identify the spatial geometry of the clay layer and its permeability. Thus, a wide range of geological and hydrogeological surveys were conducted at the Paks II NPP construction site. The main methods applied are listed below.

Engineering-geological borehole drilling

To investigate the clay layer geometry in detail, a dense net of borehole was created. It includes more than a thousand boreholes from 20 to 150 m depth, the distance between the boreholes in the vicinity of the Dunaszentgyörgy-Harta fault zone did not exceed 20 m. The core material from each well was thoroughly described and a system of the marker horizons was developed. More than 500 cone penetration tests were carried out as well as the surface and borehole geophysics survey conducted.

Groundwater level monitoring

A part of the wells drilled in the scope of the engineering-geological surveys was later used for a groundwater level monitoring system creation. A multi-level wells clusters screened to the upper (Quarternary) and lower (Pannonian) aquifers were created.

The groundwater monitoring net provides an information about the groundwater head distribution in depth and plan. Obviously, the head difference between two adjacent aquifers is than greater, than the impermeability of the separating aquitard is complete. Quantitively this relationship can be expressed in terms of the following formula (Bochever, Rumynin):

$$\Delta H_0 \approx \varepsilon L \sqrt{\frac{m'T_2}{k'T_1(T_1+T_2)}} \quad (1)$$

where ΔH_0 is the head difference, m; ε is the recharge value, m/d; L is the distance between the watershed and the discharge zone, m; k' is the hydraulic conductivity (m/d) and m' is the thickness (m) of the separating aquitard; $T_1=k_1m_1$, $T_2=k_2m_2$ are the transmissivities of the upper and below aquifers, respectively (m²/d).

Pumping tests

For quantitatively and qualitatively assessment of the clay layer's flow parameters, four pumping tests from the Pannonian aquifer were carried out with the constant discharge rate ranging from 150 to 370 m³/d. The groundwater level was simultaneously observed in 44 monitoring wells using data-loggers to analyze the dynamics of the hydraulic impact caused by the pumping.

Qualitative analysis of the pumping test is carried out using a drawdown as an indicator of the hydraulic influence presence. A monitoring net including 20, 50, 75, 100, 125 and 150 m deep wells spread all over the construction site was used for analysis. This algorithm is also known as the hydraulic tomography and described in the papers such as Berg (Berg 2011), Zhao (Zhao 2023).

Quantitative analysis of the pumping tests was carried out using the scheme of the confined infinite aquifer with Theis solution (2) (Theis 1935) (and the scheme of the leaky aquifer with the constant head in adjacent aquifer with Hantush, Jacob solution (3) (Hantush 1955):

$$s = \frac{Q}{4\pi T} W\left(\frac{r^2}{4at}\right); \quad (2)$$

$$s = \frac{Q}{4\pi T} W\left(\frac{r^2}{4Tt}, \frac{r}{B}\right) = \frac{Q}{4\pi T} W\left(\frac{r^2}{4at}, \frac{r}{B}\right), \quad (3)$$

$$W(u, \beta) = \int_u^\infty \frac{1}{\tau} \exp\left(-\tau - \frac{\beta^2}{4\tau}\right) d\tau,$$

$$B = \sqrt{\frac{Tm'}{k'}},$$

where s is drawdown in the observation well, m ; Q is the discharge rate of the pumping well, m^3/d ; $T=km$ is the transmissivity of the main aquifer m^2/d ; k, m, S are the hydraulic conductivity (m/d), thickness (m), and storage coefficient (dimensionless) of the aquifer; $a=T/S$ is the hydraulic diffusivity of the aquifer, m^2/d ; B is the leakage factor for a single adjacent aquifer, m ; k' is the hydraulic coefficient (m/d) and thickness (m) of the aquitard; r is the radial distance from the pumping to the observation well, m ; t is the time elapsed from the start of pumping, d ; $W(u, \beta)$ is the well-function for leaky aquifers (Sindalovskiy 2017).

Note that Hantush Jacob solution tends to the Theis solution if the leakage parameter B tends to infinity $B \rightarrow \infty$. This note corresponds to the physics of the process: when there is no leakage from the adjacent aquifer, the hydrogeological settings can be conceptualized with the infinite aquifer scheme.

Numerical hydrogeological modelling

The numerical modeling has widely extended the possibility of probability analysis for the hydrogeological conditions. Thus, the calibrated hydrogeological model has been used to evaluate three clay layer deformation concepts: i) no discontinuity, ii) local discontinuity, and iii) regional discontinuity (Fig. 1). Clay's layer discontinuity has been implemented into the model by setting the model blocks along the dislocation zone with high hydraulic conductivity k values. The accuracy of the model results was controlled by comparing the head difference between the upper (Quaternary) and lower (Pannonian) aquifers obtained by the model and the one observed at the construction site.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A dense network of engineering-geological boreholes has significantly enhanced an understanding of the geological structure at the Paks II construction site, yet it could not elucidate the continuity of the clay layer.

A multi-level well clusters designed to observe the groundwater level change provided the information about the hydraulic head distribution in plan and depth. The head difference between the upper (Quaternary) and lower (Pannonian) aquifers is considered as an indirect indicator of the separating clay layer's impermeability. The data obtained in the scope of the hydrogeological monitoring was used to analyze the head difference at the construction site in plan. The observed head difference (Fig. 2a) was compared with the model results, proceed for three concepts of the clay layer deformation (Fig. 2a, b, c, d).

A comparative analysis has shown that the regional discontinuity (Fig. 2d) in the clay layer leads to a drastic change in the fluid flow pattern of the Pannonian aquifer. Thus, at the zone of the clay discontinuity, the hydraulic head difference shrinks to values of 2.5–3.0 m (Fig. 2d), whereas the observed values at the Paks II NPP construction site reach 4.5–5.0 m (Fig. 2a). On this basis the regional discontinuity concept was excluded from further consideration.

Fig. 2. Map of the hydraulic head difference between the lower (Pannonian) and upper (Quarternary) aquifers: A) observed at the construction site based on the groundwater monitoring data; B) model for the no discontinuity concept; C) model for the local discontinuity concept; D) model for the regional discontinuity concept

The observed hydraulic head difference distribution (Fig. 2a) in the plan generally corresponds to the no discontinuity model concept (Fig. 2b). At the same time, an abnormal hydraulic head difference can be observed in the vicinity of the PT-2-D well (Fig. 2a). This kind of “anomaly” could be explained by a leakage through the hydrogeological window that had been formed by the vertical dislocation along the fault zone (Fig. 2c). This assumption, however, was not confirmed by the results of the pumping test from the well PT-2-D screened to the Pannonian aquifer below the clay layer.

A qualitative interpretation of the 5-day pumping test from well PT-2-D with a recharge rate of 230 m³/d has shown that not a single observation well screened to the upper aquifer has reacted to the

pumping. Meanwhile, all the observation wells screened to the Pannonian aquifer demonstrate a similar reaction to the pumping. The drawdown curves do not gradual flatten which indicates an absence of the leakage from the adjacent aquifer (Fig. 3a).

A quantitative interpretation of the pumping test meant to fit an analytically calculated drawdown curve obtained by Theis solution (2) to the observed data. Transmissivity T and hydraulic diffusivity a obtained by this way were then applied to Hantush and Jacob solution (3) to estimate the value of the leakage factor B and hydraulic conductivity k' of the aquitard. The pumping tests analysis was carried out in ANSDIMAT software (Sindalovsky).

Fig. 3. Graphs of the observed groundwater drawdown during the pumping test in the PT-2-D well: A) in a group of wells screened to the Pannonian aquifer; b) in a single well with an example of the analytical interpretation and evaluated leakage factor B and hydraulic conductivity of the aquifer k' . Legend: 1 – observed drawdown levels; 2 – Theis solution fitting curve (2); 3 – Hantush, Jacob solution fitting curve (3)

From the data provided in graphs, it can be seen that the observed drawdown can be described with the analytical fitting curves for the infinite aquifers. This proves an assumption about the continuity of the clay layer. Assessment of the hydraulic conductivity of the clay layer by the Hantush and Jacob solution gives a value of $1.5E-04$ m/d (Fig. 3b) which is in a good agreement with the k' assessment $2.3 E-04$ m/d obtained by the formula (1) (if $\Delta H_0 = 5$ m; $\varepsilon = 0.00025$ m/d; $L = 3000$ m; $m' = 10$ m; $T_1 = 900$ m/d; $T_2 = 80$ m/d).

CONCLUSION

Nuclear power plants might be seen as projects with greater accountability, which implements the availability of a large number of the input data, such as borehole drilling data accounting for several hundred units. This number, however, does not guarantee the sufficiency of the information to conceptualize the hydrogeological conditions. At the same time, the correct hydrogeological scheme is responsible for the safety and financial parts of the project.

The present study serves as an example of the comprehensive hydrogeological and geological approach's efficiency for investigating hydrogeological media. Step-by-step analysis of the information obtained by the different sources and investigation methods allowed for the exclusion of hydrogeological concepts that did not correspond to the field data.

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